

THE ROLE OF MULTIPARAMETRIC MRI IN PROSTATE CANCER

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Relevance: Prostate cancer (PCa) is the most common cancer among the male population of the world, accounting for 22.7% of all diagnosed malignant diseases (excluding non-melanoma skin cancer), and is the second leading cause of death among cancer patients..

The aim of the study. To determine the features of MR signs of MRI in prostate cancer.

Materials and methods of the study. The study was conducted at the Fedorovich Clinic and included 114 patients who underwent multiparametric MRI of the prostate gland.

Results. The analysis of the presence of organ deformation signs depending on the multiparametric MRI sign was performed among the study participants. According to the data obtained, when comparing the presence of organ deformation signs depending on the multiparametric MRI sign among the study participants, we found statistically significant differences ($p = 0.021$) (the method used: Pearson Chi-square). We analyzed the values of the apparent diffusion coefficient parameters depending on the multiparametric MRI sign among the study participants. When comparing MR differentiation of the pancreatic tumor focus depending on the multiparametric MRI sign among the study participants, we failed to identify significant differences ($p = 0.815$) (the method used: Pearson Chi-square).

Conclusion: Comparative analysis of our study depending on the multiparametric MRI feature shows significant differences and presents MRI examination as a determining factor in the diagnosis of prostate cancer..

